
THE SCIENCE OF LIES: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF DECEPTION DETECTION TECHNIQUES IN CRIMINAL INVESTIGATIONS

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ABSTRACT

Advancements in forensic science have introduced several scientific techniques aimed at assisting criminal investigations, particularly in detecting deception and uncovering concealed information. However, the use of these techniques has generated significant legal and constitutional concerns regarding their compatibility with the fundamental rights guaranteed under the Constitution of India. The Supreme Court in Selvi v. State of Karnataka held that the involuntary administration of such techniques violates the right against self-incrimination under Article 20(3) and the right to personal liberty and mental privacy under Article 21.

This research paper critically examines the scientific foundations and legal implications of deception detection techniques within the Indian criminal justice system. It analyses their historical development, reliability, and limitations, while also addressing the constitutional concerns associated with their use. The study further explores comparative legal perspectives to understand how other jurisdictions regulate such techniques. The paper argues that although deception detection techniques should not be treated as conclusive evidence, they may serve as useful investigative tools if administered voluntarily and regulated through strict procedural safeguards. It proposes that such techniques may be recognised as corroborative evidence, thereby balancing investigative efficiency with the protection of fundamental rights.

Keywords: Deception Detection, Polygraph Test, Self-Incrimination, Right to Privacy, Criminal Investigation.

INTRODUCTION

“The right to be left alone is indeed the beginning of all freedom.”
— William O. Douglas

The discovery of truth lies at the heart of the criminal justice system. A false statement has the power to convict an innocent person. Criminal investigation involves reconstruction of the crime scene, identifying offenders, and establishing evidence before the court beyond reasonable doubt. However, deliberate concealment of facts, misleading narratives, and the silence of offenders often hinder effective investigation, making the detection of deception a

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major challenge. These tests fall under the field of Forensic Psychology, which applies scientific principles to assist legal investigations. They identify physiological responses such as heart rate, skin conductivity, and breathing rate, and psychological indicators showing whether the suspect is familiar with certain information or withholding evidence. While the Polygraph mainly measures physiological responses, Narcoanalysis and Brain Mapping rely on the psychological responses of the subject. These techniques assist investigators in furthering the investigation and narrowing down suspects.

In India, such techniques are allowed only with voluntary consent of the subject. If consent is involuntary, the results are inadmissible. Courts have generally held that the results of these techniques are not admissible as evidence in order to protect the right against self-incrimination and the right to privacy guaranteed under the Constitution. This paper relies on the landmark judgment of *Selvi v. State of Karnataka* to examine the balance between fundamental rights and effective criminal investigation by analysing the development, functioning, investigative value, and constitutional implications of Deception Detection Techniques.

RESEARCH GAP AND PROBLEM

Although deception detection techniques have been widely discussed in legal and scientific literature, several gaps remain. Existing studies give limited attention to their use in complex investigations such as organised crime or terrorism, and few propose clear procedural safeguards such as consent requirements, judicial oversight, scientific standards, and limits on evidentiary use. At the same time, modern criminal investigations increasingly rely on techniques such as polygraph tests, narco-analysis, and brain mapping to obtain investigative leads. While these methods may improve investigative efficiency, they raise serious constitutional concerns relating to the right against self-incrimination under Article 20(3) and the right to privacy and personal liberty under Article 21 of the Constitution of India. In *Selvi v. State of Karnataka*, the Supreme Court held that the involuntary use of such techniques violates fundamental rights, but the judgment left uncertainty regarding their permissible scope and evidentiary value in criminal investigations

Therefore, the central problem addressed in this study is – **Whether deception detection techniques can be regulated in a manner that protects constitutional rights while still allowing their limited use as investigative tools within the criminal justice system?** The research aims to examine the constitutional limitations, scientific reliability, and possible

regulatory safeguards necessary to balance investigative efficiency with the protection of individual rights.

HISTORICAL EVOLUTION OF DECEPTION DETECTION

Early Methods of Detection

Long before the emergence of forensic science, societies relied on primitive methods to detect lies. These methods were irrational and rooted in superstitious or religious beliefs, relying on physical endurance rather than scientific reasoning. One of the earliest methods used to determine guilt or innocence was the trial by ordeal, which included ordeals by fire, water, or poison. These tests involved dangerous practices such as ingesting poison or holding a hot iron ball, based on the belief that divine intervention would protect the innocent. Oath-taking was also common in some legal systems. Individuals were required to swear before religious authorities or sacred objects, as it was believed that fear of divine punishment would prevent deception. However, these practices were later regarded as irrational and unreliable.

Emergence of Scientific Approach

In 1870, Franz Joseph Gall proposed an early method of detecting deception by studying emotions and mental traits in the accused. Together with his student Johann Gaspar Spurzheim, he argued that personality traits and mental abilities were linked to the structure of the brain and reflected in the shape of the skull. This idea led to the development of Phrenology, which attempted to identify criminal tendencies through skull examination.³ Although later discredited, phrenology encouraged the scientific study of criminal behaviour and supported the idea that certain behaviours could be linked to brain abnormalities.⁴

Around the same period, Graphology emerged as another method of analysing personality through handwriting. Formalized in 1875 by Jean-Hippolyte Michon, it was initially used to detect forged signatures and later attempted to identify traits such as honesty or deception.⁵ After World War I, its use in lie detection declined and it was mainly used for document verification and personality assessments. Another significant contribution came from Italian criminologist Cesare Lombroso, who invented an early lie detection instrument known as Lombroso's Glove, which measured blood pressure and pulse rate during questioning. He

³Nicole Rafter, "The Murderous Dutch Fiddler: Criminology, History and the Problem of Phrenology" 9(1) *Theoretical Criminology* 65 (2005).

⁴ Paul V. Trovillo, "A History of Lie Detection" 29 *J. Crim. L. & Criminology* 848 (1939).

⁵ V. Schönfeld, *Textbook of Scientific Graphology for Beginners* (Elfa Press, 2007).

believed that emotional stress caused by deception produces observable physiological reactions.⁶ Though rudimentary, his work laid the foundation for modern forensic psychology.

Contemporary Deception Detection Techniques

Following Lombroso's work, researchers developed new techniques to detect deception by studying physiological responses, brain activity, and behavioural indicators. Charles Darwin, building on the work of Guillaume Duchenne, argued that genuine emotional expressions involve involuntary facial muscle movements that are difficult to control deliberately.⁷ In the 1960s, Paul Ekman conducted cross-cultural studies on facial expressions and deception. He also developed the Facial Action Coding System (FACS), a scientific method used to identify and categorize facial movements associated with emotional expressions.⁸ With the development of neuroscience in the 1980s, researchers began studying deception through brain activity using technologies such as Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI), Positron Emission Tomography (PET), Electroencephalography (EEG), and Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS). One notable technique is Brain Fingerprinting, developed by Lawrence Farwell and Emanuel Donchin.⁹ Although these techniques remain controversial, they represent continuing efforts to apply scientific methods to criminal investigations and the criminal justice system.

SCIENTIFIC TECHNIQUES OF DECEPTION DETECTION

Even though many techniques have emerged to detect lies and uncover the truth, the most commonly used techniques include the polygraph technique, narcoanalysis and brain mapping.

Polygraph Examination

The origins of the polygraph technique trace back to the early physiological experiments of Cesare Lombroso. Modern polygraph methods have refined these early techniques. The theory behind the polygraph is that a person who is lying produces physiological responses such as increased blood pressure, heart rate, and breathing rate. To measure these responses, instruments such as cardiographs, pneumographs, cardio-cuffs and electrodes are attached to the subject's body. These record respiration, blood pressure, pulse rate, blood flow, and

⁶ Martina Vicianova, "Historical Techniques of Lie Detection" 11(3) *Europe's Journal of Psychology* 522 (2015).

⁷ Charles Darwin, *The Expression of the Emotions in Man and Animals* (John Murray, 1872; reprint 2002).

⁸ Paul Ekman & Maureen O'Sullivan, "Who Can Catch a Liar?" 46 *American Psychologist* 913 (1991).

⁹ Lawrence A. Farwell & Emanuel Donchin, "The Truth Will Out: Interrogative Polygraphy ('Lie Detection') with Event-Related Brain Potentials" 65 *Psychophysiology* 369 (1991).

galvanic skin resistance while the subject answers questions. According to this technique, deceptive answers produce physiological reactions different from normal responses.¹⁰

Three major polygraph techniques are commonly used:

1. Relevant–Irrelevant Technique
2. Control Question Technique
3. Directed Lie-Control Technique

Relevant – Irrelevant Technique was the earliest widely used method and involves asking both relevant and irrelevant questions. Relevant questions relate directly to the investigation, while irrelevant questions are neutral. The assumption is that a guilty person will react more strongly to relevant questions, whereas an innocent person will respond similarly to both. This difference is attributed to fear of detection.¹¹

Under Control Question Technique, three types of questions are asked: relevant, control, and neutral questions. Relevant questions relate to the crime under investigation, while control questions concern past wrongdoing not linked to the specific offence. Neutral questions establish a baseline response. A deceptive subject is expected to react more strongly to the relevant or control questions than to the neutral ones. In Directed Lie-Control Technique, the examiner instructs the subject to deliberately provide false answers to certain control questions involving minor transgressions.¹²

Although the polygraph is often called a “lie detector,” the term is misleading because it does not detect lies directly but measures physiological arousal that may accompany deception. Its reliability remains debated because results may produce false positives or false negatives. Physiological reactions may also occur due to nervousness, anxiety, or environmental factors rather than deception. In some cases, individuals may manipulate their responses, making the results unreliable.

Narcoanalysis Technique

¹⁰ *Laboratory Procedure Manual: Polygraph Examination* (Directorate of Forensic Science, Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of India, New Delhi, 2005).

¹¹ Murray Kleiner (ed.). *Handbook of Polygraph Testing*. San Diego: Academic Press, 2002.

¹² National Research Council, *The Polygraph and Lie Detection* (National Academies Press, Washington D.C., 2003) 33–36.

The term narcoanalysis originates from the Greek word meaning anesthesia or torpor and refers to interrogation conducted under the influence of psychotropic drugs, commonly known as “truth serum.” In this procedure, drugs from the barbiturate class, most commonly Sodium Pentothal, are administered intravenously by a qualified medical practitioner. The term narcoanalysis was introduced by J. Stephen Horsley in 1943, although earlier experiments were conducted in 1922 by Robert House using scopolamine. He observed that subjects under the drug’s influence spoke with reduced inhibition.¹³ The theory behind narcoanalysis is that the drug induces a semi-conscious state in which the subject’s inhibitions are lowered. Since lying requires fabrication and mental effort, it is believed that individuals in such a state may reveal truthful information.

Narcoanalysis examinations involve a team of professionals including a forensic psychologist, anaesthesiologist, psychiatrist, and other medical staff. In India, these tests are usually conducted in forensic laboratories or hospital operation theatres after medical evaluation of the subject’s physical and mental condition. Narcoanalysis may help investigators uncover information, corroborate testimonies, refresh memory, or narrow the investigation. However, the technique has significant limitations. Some individuals may resist the drug’s effects or provide misleading information, while others may become highly suggestible and give inaccurate statements. Subjects may also imagine events or speak about unrelated matters, making the results unreliable and of limited evidentiary value.

Brain Electrical Activation Profile (BEAP) Test

The Brain Electrical Activation Profile test, commonly known as BEAP or the P300 wave test, measures psychological responses by analysing brain activity. Unlike the polygraph, which records physiological reactions, this method attempts to determine whether a person possesses prior knowledge of crime-related information. The test measures event-related potentials (ERP) which are electrical waveforms produced by the brain in response to external stimuli. These responses reflect cognitive processes that occur when a person recognizes words, images, or concepts. By analysing these patterns, investigators attempt to determine whether the subject recognizes the information presented during the test.¹⁴ The technique is based on the discovery of the P300 wave by Samuel Sutton in 1965. During the examination, electrodes

¹³ Shivani Sharma, “Narco-Analysis Test and Constitutional Validity in India” 3(4) International Journal of Applied Research 210 (2017).

¹⁴ Andre A. Moenssens, “Brain Fingerprinting – Can it be Used to Detect the Innocence of Persons Charged with a Crime?” 70 University of Missouri–Kansas City Law Review 891 (2002).

are attached to the subject's scalp to measure brain activity using Electroencephalography (EEG). The subject is then exposed to stimuli such as words, sounds, or images related to the investigation along with unrelated stimuli. Recognition of crime-related information is expected to trigger P300 responses.¹⁵

This method later influenced the development of Brain Fingerprinting, introduced by Lawrence Farwell. Despite its advanced technology, the BEAP test has limitations.¹⁶ Recognition of crime-related information does not necessarily prove involvement in the offence, especially if the information was obtained through media or other sources. Therefore, concerns regarding interpretation and reliability continue to limit its evidentiary value in criminal investigations.

CONSTITUTIONAL AND LEGAL SAFEGUARDS GOVERNING DDTs

Self-Incrimination and Privacy

The Indian Constitution provides important safeguards for accused persons, as a person is presumed innocent until proven guilty. Even undertrial prisoners are entitled to protection of their fundamental rights. Article 20(3) guarantees the right against self-incrimination and states that "No person accused of any offence shall be compelled to be a witness against himself." This provision ensures that an accused person has the right to remain silent and cannot be forced to confess guilt. This protection exists to prevent wrongful convictions, since individuals may otherwise be compelled through coercion, threats, or third-degree methods to admit crimes they did not commit.

The right against self-incrimination is closely related to the right to silence. This principle is reflected in Section 180(2) of the Bharatiya Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita, 2023, which states that a person must answer questions during investigation except those that may expose them to criminal charges or penalties. The Supreme Court recognised this protection in *Nandini Sathpathy v. P.L. Dani*, holding that an accused cannot be compelled to answer questions that may incriminate them.¹⁷

Another significant protection is provided under Article 21 of the Constitution, which guarantees the right to life and personal liberty. Judicial interpretation has expanded its scope

¹⁵ *Laboratory Procedure Manual: Brain Electrical Activation Profile* (Directorate of Forensic Science, Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of India, New Delhi, 2005).

¹⁶ Lawrence A. Farwell, "Brain Fingerprinting: A New Paradigm in Criminal Investigations and Counter-Terrorism" (2001), available at: www.brainwavescience.com (last visited Mar. 2, 2026).

¹⁷ *Nandini Satpathy v. P.L. Dani*, AIR 1978 SC 1025.

to include privacy, bodily integrity, and mental autonomy. In *Maneka Gandhi v. Union of India*, the Court recognised privacy as an essential component of personal liberty. In this context, the forced administration of deception detection techniques constitutes an intrusion into an individual's physical and psychological domain, violating both privacy and the protection against self-incrimination.¹⁸ However, the State also has a duty to investigate crimes effectively. Therefore, a balance must be maintained between efficient criminal investigation and the protection of fundamental rights.

Judicial Interpretations Regarding DDTs

Deception detection techniques have been used in several criminal investigations, including the Telgi stamp scam and the Aarushi Talwar murder case. Although such tests were used to guide investigations, courts have generally been reluctant to accept their results as reliable evidence. The protection under Article 20(3) extends beyond statements made in court and also applies during earlier stages such as police investigations. In *State of Bombay v. Kathi Kalu Oghad*, the Supreme Court clarified that the protection against self-incrimination applies once a person is formally accused, even before the trial begins.¹⁹ However, in *Ramchandra Ram Reddy v. State of Maharashtra*, the Bombay High Court held that techniques such as P300 brain mapping and narcoanalysis could be used during investigations as they may help investigators uncover concealed information.²⁰ The constitutional validity of these techniques was ultimately settled in the landmark judgment of *Selvi v. State of Karnataka*.

Analysis of Selvi v. State of Karnataka

In this case, the Supreme Court examined whether the involuntary administration of deception detection techniques violates constitutional rights.²¹ The Court considered four key issues:

1. Whether involuntary administration violates the right against self-incrimination under Article 20(3).
2. Whether such techniques create a likelihood of incrimination.
3. Whether the results amount to testimonial compulsion.

¹⁸ *Maneka Gandhi v. Union of India*, AIR 1978 SC 597, at 622.

¹⁹ *State of Bombay v. Kathi Kalu Oghad*, AIR 1961 SC 1808.

²⁰ *Ramchandra Ram Reddy v. State of Maharashtra*, 2004 Cri LJ 3155 (Bom).

²¹ *Selvi v. State of Karnataka*, (2010) 7 SCC 263.

4. Whether involuntary administration violates personal liberty under Article 21.

The Court held that involuntary administration of these techniques is unconstitutional as it violates the right against self-incrimination. Statements obtained during such tests are derived from the mental processes of the subject and therefore amount to testimonial compulsion. The Court also observed that these techniques may lead to wrongful incrimination, especially when individuals under the influence of drugs or psychological pressure make inaccurate statements.

Further, the Court held that these techniques interfere with personal liberty, bodily integrity, and mental privacy protected under Article 21. However, the Court did not completely prohibit their use. It ruled that only involuntary administration is unconstitutional, while voluntary tests conducted with informed consent may be permissible. The Court also clarified that the results of such tests cannot be treated as substantive evidence and may only assist investigators in discovering material evidence.

Furthermore, the National Human Rights Commission of India issued guidelines in 2000 regarding the use of neuroscientific techniques in criminal investigations. The key guidelines include:

1. The test must be conducted only with the voluntary consent of the subject.
2. The subject must have access to legal counsel and be informed of the consequences of the test.
3. The test requires permission from a Magistrate.
4. The subject must be represented by a lawyer during the hearing before the Magistrate.
5. Statements made during the test cannot be treated as confessions but only as statements similar to those made before police.
6. The Magistrate must consider factors such as the nature of interrogation and length of detention.
7. The test should be conducted by an independent medical agency such as a hospital and recorded in the presence of a lawyer.
8. A complete medical and factual record of the procedure must be maintained.²²

²² Id.

COMPARATIVE JURISPRUDENCE ON DECEPTION DETECTION TECHNIQUES

United States of America

The debate on the admissibility of deception detection techniques is not confined to India but exists across several jurisdictions. While such techniques may assist investigations, courts remain cautious because of concerns regarding reliability and protection of fundamental rights. The United States was among the earliest jurisdictions to experiment with polygraph tests in criminal investigations. However, courts have generally been reluctant to accept polygraph results as evidence due to doubts about their scientific accuracy. In *Frye v. United States*, the court held that scientific evidence must be sufficiently established and generally accepted within the relevant scientific community before it can be admitted in court.²³ This principle came to be known as the “general acceptance test.”

The law relating to scientific evidence was later refined in *Daubert v. Merrell Dow Pharmaceuticals*, where the Supreme Court laid down criteria to determine the reliability of scientific techniques. These include whether the method can be tested, whether it has been subjected to peer review, its potential error rate, the existence of operational standards, and its acceptance within the scientific community.²⁴ As a result, polygraph and similar techniques in the United States may be used as investigative tools but are rarely admitted as evidence in court. In most cases, their admissibility requires the consent of both the prosecution and the defence and is subject to strict judicial scrutiny.

European Perspective on DDTs

Many European jurisdictions are similarly cautious about the use of deception detection techniques. These countries place strong emphasis on protecting individual rights such as personal autonomy, privacy, and the right against self-incrimination. These principles are safeguarded under the European Convention on Human Rights, particularly Article 6, which guarantees the right to a fair trial.

In *Saunders v. United Kingdom*, the court held that compelling a person to provide evidence that may incriminate them violates the right to a fair trial.²⁵ Similarly, in *Funke v. France*, it

²³ *Frye v. United States*, 293 F. 1013 (D.C. Cir. 1923), <https://law.justia.com/cases/federal/appellate-courts/F2/293/1013/1476390/> (last visited Mar. 3, 2026).

²⁴ *Daubert v. Merrell Dow Pharmaceuticals*, 509 U.S. 579 (1993)

²⁵ *Saunders v. United Kingdom*, (1996) 23 EHRR 313 (ECtHR).

was held that authorities cannot compel an individual to produce evidence that may incriminate themselves.²⁶ Courts have also emphasised strict standards for expert evidence. In *R v. Turner*, it was held that expert opinion is admissible only when it assists the court on matters beyond ordinary knowledge and is provided by a qualified and impartial expert.²⁷ This principle was further clarified in *R v. Bonython*, which required expert opinions to be based on a recognised and established body of knowledge.²⁸

Comparative Analysis

A comparative study shows that deception detection techniques are generally not accepted as reliable evidence across jurisdictions. The United States has developed evidentiary standards to evaluate scientific evidence but continues to treat such techniques with caution. European jurisdictions place greater emphasis on protecting individual rights such as privacy and the privilege against self-incrimination. India follows a similar approach, where constitutional protections take precedence over investigative convenience. Although such techniques may sometimes be used as investigative tools, their results are rarely treated as substantive evidence and are primarily used to assist investigations or obtain further leads.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR BALANCING NECESSITY WITH FUNDAMENTAL RIGHTS

The controversy surrounding deception detection techniques is mainly because of the tensions between investigative need and constitutional safeguards. While the Supreme Court held the involuntary administration of such techniques to be unconstitutional, it was not completely prohibited. If a balance is achieved, it creates an opportunity for the admissibility of such techniques with proper procedural and legal safeguards. Several measures can be taken for this. Firstly, the main problem lies in the lack of proper legislation to regulate the use of such techniques. If an act for “Regulation of Scientific Interrogation” was enacted, then this could make such techniques legitimate under rule of law instead of this being a discretion of investigative agencies. Such act has to clearly mention the following:

1. Permissible techniques
2. Qualification of examiner

²⁶ *Funke v. France*, (1993) 16 EHRR 297 (ECtHR).

²⁷ *R v. Turner*, [1975] QB 834 (CA).

²⁸ *R v. Bonython*, (1984) 38 SASR 45 (SASC).

3. Procedural Safeguards
4. Conditions for admissibility
5. Penalties for misuse

Such a statutory framework can strengthen admissibility of these techniques in court. Secondly, the courts have always been wary of these techniques because of the doubts regarding scientific reliability as there could be technical fallacies. For this, India could adopt a structured evidentiary framework like in the case of *Daubert v. Merrell Dow Pharmaceuticals*. Under such framework, courts can establish specific criteria to evaluate these scientific techniques such as:

1. Scientific reliability of the test
2. Peer-reviewed research about the techniques
3. Calculation of error rates
4. Conditions under which the test was administered
5. Necessity of test depending on nature of case
6. Acceptance within scientific community

If the techniques satisfy such standards, the courts may consider them as expert evidence rather than conclusive evidence. Thirdly, the results of these techniques can be admissible as corroborative evidence rather than treating it as direct evidence. Under this, the test can independently establish guilt but it must be supported by other material evidence and the tests can assist the courts in evaluating credibility of witnesses or other investigative leads.

Another recommendation would be the establishment of a National Scientific Interrogation Oversight Authority. The primary functions of this body would include:

1. Accrediting laboratories conduction deception detection tests
2. Train examiners and certify them
3. Establish uniform procedure for testing
4. Periodical investigation of agencies for any violation

Such institutional oversight may increase the credibility of these tests in court. Furthermore, it is imperative to ensure that such techniques maintain ethical safeguards and do not involve any threat or degrading treatment, respect bodily integrity and in no way should cause bodily harm to the subject, should be used only in serious criminal matters and any legislation or other actions related to this test should fall under the purview of judicial review. A proper balance

between investigative efficiency and constitutional safeguards is required for admissibility of these tests.

CONCLUSION

The development of scientific methods for detecting deception has influenced modern criminal investigations. Techniques such as polygraph examinations, narco-analysis, and brain electrical activation profile (BEAP) tests were introduced to help investigators uncover concealed information and assist in complex cases. However, their use has generated significant constitutional debate regarding the protection of individual rights. In *Selvi v. State of Karnataka*, the Supreme Court held that the involuntary administration of such techniques violates the right against self-incrimination and the right to personal liberty and mental privacy, though the Court did not completely prohibit their voluntary use with safeguards.

This research examined the scientific basis, development, and legal implications of deception detection techniques. Although these methods may assist investigations, their reliability remains debated and their intrusive nature raises ethical and constitutional concerns. Therefore, treating their results as direct or conclusive evidence would be inconsistent with the principles of fair trial and due process. However, the study suggests that these techniques should not be entirely excluded from the investigative process. When properly regulated, they may serve as investigative tools and corroborative evidence in complex cases. A balanced framework involving legislative regulation, scientific validation, judicial oversight, and strict procedural safeguards is therefore necessary. Ultimately, the challenge is to balance investigative efficiency with the protection of fundamental rights while ensuring both effective investigations and the safeguarding of individual liberties.

REFERENCES

Books

1. Hall, C. S. & Lindzey, G., *Psychology of Personality* (SPN, Bratislava, 2002).
2. Michon, J. H., *Textbook of Scientific Graphology for Beginners* (Elfa Press, Praha, 2007).
3. Poizner, A., *Clinical Graphology: An Interpretive Manual for Mental Health Practitioners* (Charles C. Thomas, Springfield, IL, 2012).

Journal Articles

1. Rafter, N., "The Murderous Dutch Fiddler: Criminology, History and the Problem of Phrenology" 9 *Theoretical Criminology* 65 (2005).
2. Trovillo, P. V., "A History of Lie Detection" 29 *Journal of Criminal Law and Criminology* 848 (1939).
3. Thomas, S. L., "The Write Stuff: What the Evidence Says About Using Handwriting Analysis in Hiring" 66 *SAM Advanced Management Journal* 31 (2001).
4. Moenssens, Andre A., "Brain Fingerprinting – Can It Be Used to Detect the Innocence of Persons Charged with a Crime?" 70 *UMKC Law Review* 891 (2002).
5. New, John G., "If You Could Read My Mind – Implications of Neurological Evidence for Twenty-First Century Criminal Jurisprudence" 29 *Journal of Legal Medicine* 179 (2008).
6. Dession, George H., Freedman, Lawrence Z., Donnelly, Richard C. & Redlich, Frederick G., "Drug-Induced Revelation and Criminal Investigation" 62 *Yale Law Journal* 315 (1953).

Online Sources

1. "Detection of Deception: Cognitive Load," available at: <https://criminal-justice.iresearchnet.com/forensic-psychology/police-psychology/detection-of-deception-cognitive-load/>.
2. "Narcoanalysis – The Science Behind Truth Serums," available at: <https://www.medindia.net/health/diagnosis/narcoanalysis-the-science-behind-truth-serums.htm>
3. "Constitutionality of Narco Test," available at: <https://www.livelaw.in/lawschool/articles/constitutionality-of-narco-test-164554>
4. Farwell, Lawrence A., "Brain Fingerprinting: A New Paradigm in Criminal Investigations and Counter-Terrorism," available at: www.brainwavescience.com